

Effectiveness of Progressive Muscle Relaxation Technique on Test anxiety among the students in the selected schools of the city

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ABSTRACT:

Feeling of anxiety is so common in our society that they are almost considered universal. Anxiety arises from the chaos and confusion that exists in the world today. Fears of the unknown and conditions of ambiguity offer a perfect breeding ground for anxiety to take root and grow. Low levels of anxiety are adaptive and can provide the motivation required for survival. It becomes problematic when the individual is unable to prevent the anxiety from escalating to a level that interferes with the ability to meet basic needs. PMR or active relaxation is a technique in which the individuals attain relaxation through active contraction of a group of special muscles and then releasing them in a progressive manner and reach self-peace. Based on new research, complete relaxation can be felt as a result of practicing this technique at least for four or five sessions. In this study, Non randomized control group design was used to assess the effectiveness of Progressive Muscle Relaxation Technique on Test anxiety among the school going students. Study was conducted in the selected school in the city. The approval for the study was granted by Principal of the school. The setting was selected due to availability of samples, feasibility of conducting study, and ethical clearance. In present study, Non probability convenient sampling technique was used for the selection of the samples. Group of 102 students selected from selected school in the city. 51 cases in each group i.e experimental and control group respectively. Standardized Hamilton anxiety rating scale was used for anxiety. Study result shown that total of 102 students participated in the study, comprising 58.82% males and 41.17% females. Pre-test assessment revealed that 10.78% had mild, 53.92% moderate, and 35.29% severe test anxiety. Moderate test anxiety was observed in 37 male and 18 female students. The experimental group showed a significant reduction in test anxiety following the implementation of Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR) technique, with the mean anxiety score decreasing from 24.25 in the pre-test to 14.49 in the post-test, indicating the effectiveness of PMR in reducing test anxiety among students.

Introduction

Feeling of anxiety is so common in our society that they are almost considered universal. Anxiety arises from the chaos and confusion that exists in the world today. Fears of the unknown and conditions of ambiguity offer a perfect breeding ground for anxiety to take root and grow. Low levels of anxiety are adaptive and can provide the motivation required for survival. It becomes problematic when the individual is unable to prevent the anxiety from escalating to a level that interferes with the ability to meet basic needs.⁴ Anxiety is a normal reaction to certain situations. A small level of anxiety is normal, but severe anxiety can be a serious problem. Academic anxiety can become more detrimental over time. As a student's academic performance suffers, the anxiety level related to certain academic tasks increases.⁵ Frequently, anxiety is seen and diagnosed in school aged children and adolescents. Approximately 8-12% of children meet some criteria for an anxiety disorder.⁶ One of the suggested methods to reduce anxiety is relaxation,⁷ of which one of the most applicable techniques is progressive muscle relaxation (PMR). PMR or active relaxation is a technique in which the individuals attain relaxation through active contraction of a group of special muscles and then releasing them in a progressive manner and reach self-peace. Based on new research, complete relaxation can be felt as a result of practicing this technique at least for four or five sessions.⁸

Chinyelu Nwokolo, Mokwelu Obianuju Blessing and Umezulike Roseline Ekwutosi. Quasi-experimental research study conducted with sample size of 68 adolescents in SS1 with test anxiety. The sample was derived using purposive sampling technique based on the number of students who scored high on test anxiety. Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) was used for data collection. Findings revealed reduction of test anxiety after progressive muscle relaxation technique in secondary school students' and significantly differ with that of the conventional counseling group. Pretest and posttest mean loss scores of test anxiety on PMRT Tech. and control group is 11.54 and 6. Hence, significantly reduced the test anxiety of the participants.⁹

Heidi A et. al. conducted a study with 177 students, to study the effect of relaxation technique on test anxiety. Students at one school were taught relaxation techniques, while students at the second school served as the control group, with no training. The results indicated that the relaxation intervention had a significant effect in reducing test anxiety in the experimental group. Whereas, no significant decrease in test anxiety found in the control group. For both experimental subgroups, significant differences between the pre-test and post-test means were found ($t(55) = 2.24, p = 0.029$

and $t(67) = 4.07$, $p = 0.000$, respectively). These results indicated that the relaxation intervention had a significant effect in reducing test anxiety. By contrast, no significant difference was found between the control group's pre- and post-test means ($t(52) = 0.39$, $p = 0.699$).¹⁰

Thus, in the present study, effectiveness of Progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the school going students was assessed.

Problem statement

“Effectiveness of Progressive Muscle Relaxation Technique on Test anxiety among the students in the selected schools of the city.”

Objectives:

1. To assess the test anxiety among the student in the selected schools of the city.
2. To determine the effectiveness of progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the students in selected schools of the city.
3. To find the association of study findings with selected demographic variables.

Hypothesis:

1. **H₀**: There is no significant effect of Progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the students in selected schools of the city.
2. **H₁**: There is significant effect of Progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the students in selected schools of the city.

Methodology:

Research Approach

Quantitative Research approach

Research design

In this study, Non randomized control group design was used to assess the effectiveness of Progressive Muscle Relaxation Technique on Test anxiety among the school going students.

Keeping in view the objective of the study, the researcher selected Quasi experimental Non Randomized control group design.

Fig.No: 1, Study Design

Keys:

Group - Students from selected schools of the city.

01(pre-test) - An assessment of test anxiety among the students.

X - Administer the progressive muscle relaxation technique.

02(post-test) - Assessment of test anxiety after administration of progressive muscle relaxation technique.

Setting of the Study

Study was conducted in the selected school in the city. The approval for the study was granted by Principal of the school. The setting was selected due to availability of samples, feasibility of conducting study, and ethical clearance.

Variables

In the present study, the Independent variable is Progressive muscle relaxation technique and Dependent variable is Test anxiety.

Sampling technique

Only those fulfilled the Inclusion criteria were selected for the study. In present study, Non probability convenient sampling technique was used for the selection of the samples. Group of 102 students selected from selected school in the city.

Sample Size

51 cases in each group i.e experimental and control group respectively.

Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

1. Students willing to participate in study, consents from parents.
2. Students from Std. 8th and 9th class.
3. Age group from 13-15 years.
4. Able to understand English language.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Students not available during study.
2. Earlier benefited by Progressive Muscle relaxation technique

Description of tool

Section A: Demographic variables (Age, Gender, Parent occupation, Tuitions, exam score, Any exposure to relaxation technique and Practice before appearing for exam to reduce test anxiety)

Section B: Standardized Hamilton anxiety rating scale. Each item is scored on a scale of 0 (not present) to 4 (severe), with a total score range of 0–56.

Plan for data analysis

1. Organize the statistical data in a master sheet.
2. Demographic data would be analysed using descriptive statistical method.

Descriptive Statistics: Demographic variables and levels of pre-test and post-test scores will be given in frequencies with their percentages. Mean and standard deviation will be calculated.

Inferential Statistics: Pre-test and post-test differences of test anxiety among the students in selected schools of the city will be analyzed using paired t – test and association of study findings with demographic variables will be analyzed using Pearson Chi-square test.

Ethical aspects:

1. A study conducted only after approval from ethical committee.
2. The permission obtained from the concerned authority.
3. Informed written consent and ascent taken from the participants and their parents.
4. The information given by the subjects kept confidential.

Data generated during the research process was used extensively for benefits of the profession.

Progressive muscle relaxation technique procedure

Dr. Edmund Jacobson invented the technique in the 1920's as a way to help his patients deal with anxiety. Dr. Jacobson felt that relaxing the muscles could relax the mind as well. The technique involves tightening one muscle group while keeping the rest of the body relaxed, and then releasing the tension.

Steps:

For each muscle group, tense for 10 seconds and release, taking a few deep breaths as you notice sensation that comes as those muscles relax, before moving on to the next muscle group. Skip areas that cause pain when tensing.

1. Sit in a comfortable position, with eyes closed. Take a few deep breaths, expanding your belly as you breathe air in and contracting it as you exhale.
2. Begin at the top of your body, and go down. Start with your head, tensing your facial muscles, squeezing your eyes shut, puckering your mouth and clenching your jaw. Hold, then release and breathe.
3. Tense as you lift your shoulders to your ears, hold, then release and breathe.

4. Make a fist with your right hand, tighten the muscles in your lower and upper arm, hold, then release. Breathe in and out. Repeat with left hand.
5. Concentrate on your back, squeezing shoulder blades together. Hold, then release. Breathe in and out.
6. Suck in your stomach, hold, then release. Breathe in and out.
7. Clench your buttocks, hold, then release. Breathe in and out.
8. Tighten your right hamstring, hold, then release. Breathe in and out. Repeat with left hamstring.
9. Flex your right calf, hold, then release. Breathe in and out. Repeat with left calf.
10. Tighten toes on your right foot, hold, then release. Breathe in and out. Repeat with left foot.¹¹

RESULT

The collected data is tabulated, analyzed, organized and presented under the following headings:

Section I: It deals with the analysis of demographic data of students.

Section II: It deals with the analysis of data related to the level of test anxiety among students in the experimental and control group.

Section III: It deals with the analysis of data related to the effectiveness of progressive muscle relaxation technique among students in the experimental and control group.

Section IV: Analysis of data related to the association test anxiety of students with their demographic profile.

Section I: Description of samples based on their personal characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage.

Table No: 1, Group wise description of Demographic Characteristics

N:E=51,C=51

Sr. No.	Variables	Experimental group		Control group	
		Frequency	Percentage %	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Age				
A	13-14	23	45.1	27	52.9
B	14-15	28	54.9	24	47.1
2.	Gender				
A	Male	31	60.8	29	39.2
B	Female	20	56.9	22	43.1
3.	Parent Occupation				
A	Both working	12	23.53	10	19.61
B	Father Working	37	72.54	41	80.39
C	Mother working	2	3.93	0	0
4.	Tutions				
A	Yes	40	78.43	34	66.66
B	No	11	21.56	17	33.33
5.	Exam score				
A	Upto 60%	27	52.94	26	50.98
B	Above 60%	24	47.05	25	49.01

6.	Any exposure to relaxation technique				
A	Yes	28	54.9	26	51.0
B	No	23	45.1	25	49.0
7.	School Time				
A	Morning	51	100	51	100
8.	Practice before appearing examination to reduce the test anxiety.				
A	Meditation	16	31.37	23	45.09
B	Listen music	30	58.82	26	50.98
C	Any other	5	9.80	2	3.92

Section II: It deals with the analysis of data related to the level of test anxiety among students in the experimental and control group.

Table No: 2, Pre-existing level of Test anxiety among the school going students in selected area of city.

N: E=51,C=51

Sr.No.	Test Anxiety level	Experimental group		Control group	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	Mild	2	3.93	9	17.65
2	Moderate	30	58.82	25	49.01
3	Severe	19	37.25	17	33.34
Total		51	100	51	100

Fig. No: 2, Description of Pre-existing level of Test anxiety among Students

This graph describes that the students have Test anxiety from mild to severe. Majority of students shows Moderate level of Test anxiety with the frequency of 30 students in experimental group and 25 students in control group. About 19 students from experimental group have severe test anxiety and 17 students from control group have severe test anxiety.

Section III: It deals with the analysis of data related to the effectiveness of progressive muscle relaxation technique on Test anxiety among students in the experimental and control group.

1. Table No: 3, Effectiveness of Progressive muscle relaxation technique on Test anxiety among students.

N: E=51

Sr.No.	Test Anxiety level	Experimental group			
		Pre-test score		Post test score	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	Mild	2	3.93	39	76.47
2	Moderate	30	58.82	7	13.72

3	Severe	19	37.25	5	9.81
Total		51	100	51	100

Fig. No: 3, Description of effectiveness of Progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the school going students.

This diagram is showing the effectiveness of Progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the school going students in terms of frequency.

In the Experimental group, 2 students had mild test anxiety, 30 students had moderate test anxiety and 19 students had severe test anxiety before intervention.

After intervention the 39 students were having mild test anxiety, 7 and 5 students were found to have moderate and severe test anxiety. The number of students was reduced in the moderate and severe category of test anxiety.

2. Table no: 4, Paired t-test for the Effectiveness of Progressive Muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the school going students.

N: 51

Experimental group	Mean	SD	df	t value
Pre-test	24.25	6.81	50	11.32
Post-test	14.49	5.65		

Fig. No: 4, Description based on Average Test Anxiety among Students in Experimental group

This diagram is showing average test anxiety among the school going students in the Experimental group before and after Intervention.

Paired t-test was used to analyze the average test anxiety score among the school going students in the experimental group. Average Test anxiety score in the pre-test was 24.25 which was reduced to 14.49 after the intervention in the post test. It shows that the t value is 11.32, which was larger than ($p < 0.05$), hence null hypothesis rejected.

3. Table. No: 5, Two sample unpaired t-test for the comparison of experimental and control group for the effectiveness of progressive muscle relaxation technique on the test anxiety among the school going students.

Both (experimental and control group) values

N: E=51, C=51

Score at	Number of students	Test anxiety level		
		df	t value	p-value
Experimental	51	50	10.64	0.52
Control	51	50		

Researcher applied unpaired t-test for the effectiveness Progressive muscle relaxation technique on test anxiety among the students in selected schools of the city, the t-value is 10.64 with 50 degrees of freedom and the corresponding p-value is 0.52, which indicates the $p < 0.05$ hence the null hypothesis is rejected and Progressive Muscle relaxation technique is significantly effective on test anxiety among students in selected schools of the city.

Section IV: Analysis of data related to the association test anxiety of students with their demographic profile.

Table No: 6, Analysis of data related to the association of test anxiety of students with their demographic profile.

Sr. No.	Variables	Mild	Mild to moderate	Moderate to Severe	Chi-square test	p-value
1.	Age				3.250	0.204
A	13-14	8	27	15		Not Significant
B	14-15	3	28	21		

2.	Gender				6.870	0.033 Significant
A	Male	8	37	15		
B	Female	3	18	21		
3.	Parent Occupation				3.880	0.496 Not Significant
A	Both working	2	12	8		
B	Father Working	9	43	26		
C	Mother working	0	0	2		
4.	Tuitions				6.390	0.038 Significant
A	Yes	10	43	21		
B	No	1	12	15		
5.	Exam score				3.120	0.232 Not Significant
A	Upto 60%	3	31	19		
B	Above 60%	8	24	17		
6.	Any exposure to relaxation technique				0.193	0.958 Not Significant
A	Yes	6	30	18		
B	No	5	25	18		

Hence, the data analysis showing the association of Demographic variables was done. The result showed that variables i.e Gender and Tuitions have significant association with the pre-existing level of test anxiety. The findings are 0.033 and 0.038 which smaller than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

In the present study there were total 102 samples among it Male were 58.82% and Females were 41.17 %

Farhad Ghorban Dordi Nejad, et all. In this study, there were 150 participants categorized as 70 male (46.7%) and 80 female students (53.3%).¹²

In the present study there were students suffering from test anxiety i.e Mild test anxiety 11 students (10.78%), Moderate test anxiety 55 students (53.92%) and Severe test anxiety 36 (35.29).

Ponnusamy, A descriptive study on Examination Anxiety among 50 students of a recognized School. The result showed that 40% of the students had moderate level of examination anxiety, and 24% with severe levels of examination anxiety.¹³

In the present study 37 Male students and 18 female students had Moderate levels of Test anxiety score.

Similar to present study, gender difference is reported on anxiety among children in school setting, girls reported higher anxiety on all anxiety subscales than boy.¹⁴

Deb S, Chatterjee P, Walsh K., However, Indian study at Kolkata found a contrasting significant higher anxiety in boys (20.1%) as compared to girls (17.9%).¹⁵

In the present study, the Experimental group had the Pre-test mean as 24.25 and after the implementation of Progressive Muscle relaxation technique the post-test mean is 14.49 hence, the reduction in the mean score is suggestive of effective Progressive muscle relaxation technique on Test anxiety.

Praseeda P, K. P. Meera, the study found the effect of Progressive Muscle Relaxation for reducing the academic stress of secondary school students. The Mean Pre-test score was 168.85 and the Post-test score was 137.92 Hence, The post test mean score is significantly lower than pre-test score which clearly proves that Progressive Muscle relaxation is effective in reducing academic stress in classroom situation for the total sample..¹⁶

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. A similar study with longer duration can be conducted to assess the long term benefits of progressive muscle relaxation technique.
2. A similar study can be conducted by having a control group to observe the value of other complementary therapy.
3. A comparative study can be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of progressive muscle relaxation technique with other various complementary therapies among the College going students.
4. A similar study can be conducted with large sample size and in different state.

CONCLUSION

The results showed that performing progressive muscle relaxation technique was effective in reducing test anxiety among students. It is suggested to conduct educational programs concerning this method in the School teaching faculties to decrease the test anxiety of student.

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